

China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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Abstract

China Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is a huge project executed by the People's Republic of China and Islamic Republic of Pakistan. CPEC has bright prospects but it might face challenges in the process of execution. In the recent days, tremendous literature is coming up on the subject in the form of books, monographs, research papers and other write ups, in the print and social media. Nevertheless, very few of them are based on direct contact with people. Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan is a key partner in execution of the project. . From the boundaries of Gilgit Baltistan to Rawalpindi district of the Punjab Province, the main route of the corridor passes through that strategically important province. Furthermore a number of projects of CPEC will also be executed in the province. This paper is an attempt to look into the CPEC prospects in the province especially people's opinion and support for it. For this purpose, respondents, selected through convenient sampling, were approached. They belonged to wide range of areas and socio-economic backgrounds. Views of the respondents were analyzed so as to reach conclusion. Moreover, few more respondents were selected for key informant interviews in order to get their views for qualitative analysis.

Introduction

For the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, five major and some other projects under CPEC have been approved. Detail has been given in the following table:

S. No	Project	Sector	Cost in UD dollars
1.	Sukai Kinari Hydro power Station Naraan	Energy	1704 million
2.	Burhan Havelian Express way (PSDP)	Infrastructure	Rs.34165 million
3.	KKH Phase II (Thakot -Havelian Section) 118 Km	do	1315 Million
4.	KKH Thakot-Raikot N35 remaining portion (136 Km) (PSDP)	do	Rs. 136659 Million
5.	Havelian Dry port (450 M. Twenty-Foot Equivalent Units)	do	65 million
6.	Greater Peshawar Region Mass Transit is under process	Railway
7.	Rashakai Economic Zone , M-1, Nowshera	Special Economic Zones
8.	Hakla D.I Khan Motorway 285 Km	Infrastructure	Rs.110208 million
9.	Improvement and widening of Chitral-Boni-mastuj-Shandur	do	Rs. 16755 Million
10.	Construction of Zonal CPEC office in Mansehra (PSDP)	do	Rs.59.00 Million
11.	Widening and improvement of Peshawar-Rawalpindi Railway tract.	Railway

Source: The above detail was gathered from Government of Pakistan sources and Pakistan China Institute cited at the end. Besides the projects mentioned in the table above, the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province may also benefit from the projects in pipeline.

The Sukai Kinari Hydro power Station Naraan is a joint venture of Chinese, Saudi Arabian and Malaysian companies. It will be constructed and executed on BoT (Build-Own-Operate and Transfer) basis. It is run-of-the-river largest private sector hydropower project located on Kunhar River in the Kaghan Valley. Right now, it is in the process of completion. On commission, it will generate 870 Megawatts of electricity. On transfer to the government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, it will earn Rs. 1.5 billion for the province every year.

The Rashakai Special Economic Zone (SEZ), is one of the nine such economic zones to be established in other parts of Pakistan. Initially it was planned that 27 SEZs will be established but then the number was reduced to nine. The other SEZs are going to be established in Dhabeji, Bostan, Faisalabad, Islamabad, Karachi, Mirpur Azad Kashmir, Mohmand and Gilgit-Baltistan.

The aim of these SEZs is to relocate the Chinese industries and enter into joint ventures with Pakistani businessmen for exports goods producing industries under the umbrella of China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC). Rashakai is a town situated on Mardan Nowshera road. Besides other peculiarities, the town is known for its big cloth market which attracts people from all parts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Punjab and federal capital Islamabad. Although the proposed Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is not going to be belt in proper Rashakai, and the site of the project is at a little distance from the main town on Peshawar Islamabad motorway M1.

The Hazara motorway is one of the most significant projects of CPEC passing through the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province. It will be main route of the corridor. It originates from Peshawar-Islamabad motorway M-1 a little ahead of Burhan interchange. From there it passes near Haripur and then Havelian. From Havelian it runs towards Abbottabad, and then Mansehra and Shinkiari. The end point is Thakot in Batagram District. The Hazara Motorway has five tunnels two at Abbottabad and one each at Battal, Karmong and Mansehra. Up to Haripur it is six-lane controlled access while from Havelian to Mansehra portion is four lanes. Mansehra-Thakot section has 2 lanes. The second section of the motorway i.e. Havelian to Mansehra was opened in January 2020. It was further reported that the remaining part i.e. Mansehra-Thakot section was planned to be inaugurated in June 2020 but due to COVID-19 pandemic, it was delayed.

The rehabilitation of Peshawar-Rawalpindi Railway track (ML-1) is actually part of the greater project titled as “Rehabilitation & Up-gradation of Karachi-Lahore Peshawar (ML-1) Railway Track” which is 1,872 kilometers long. With the completion of this project, railways transport will receive a boost and dependence on vehicular road transport will be reduced. The project is in the initial stages and its PC-1 was approved by Central Development Working Party (CDWP) on 6th June 2020. The project has the following features:

- Doubling of entire track from Peshawar to Rawalpindi
- Speed of passenger trains to be raised to 160 kilometers per hour
- Freight trains to operate at a speed of 120 kilometers per hour
- The signaling and control system will be digitalized.

- In order to avoid accidents, grade separation system will be introduced.

The widening and improvement of Chitral-Shandur road was badly needed. The PC-1 of the project has already been approved. The total length from Chitral to Shandur is 153 kilometers. The road starts from Chitral and runs towards north parallel to Mastuj River till Booni. It crosses the towns of Mori Payeen, Maroi, Pret, Barenis, Green Lasht, Reshun, Cherun, Jonali Cooch and reaches Booni. From Booni, the alignment turns towards East and reaches Mastuj after crossing Parwak. From Mastuj it turns towards south and then runs parallel to Laspur River to meet Shandur, passing through Onshit, Shaidas, Ghasht, Raman, Harchin, Brook, Balim and Surlaspur. It was reported that from Shandur onward, it will be extended to Gilgit Baltistan. With the completion of this project, not only that the adjacent areas will be developed but tourism will also be increased. Tourism will not only fetch revenue but it will trigger economic activities in the region which will, in due course of time, improve lot of the people.

The share of projects given to the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa may not be enough but they are important in many ways. The province will certainly benefit from them. The question whether people of the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are satisfied or not with the CPEC can only be answered through empirical investigation. This paper has attempted to analyze empirically the perception of people. So in the following pages, literature review, interviews, and methodology in general, designing of research, particularly tool of data collection and details of survey have been given. The data collected has been analyzed and conclusions have been drawn.

One of the results of CPEC is that thousands of Pakistani students have got Chinese scholarships. A large number of them have completed PhD and post-docs while many more are studying in universities in the length and breadth of China.

The Higher Education Commission Pakistan (HEC) and China Association of Higher Education (CAHE) are in close contact with each other. Both the countries have established consortium of Universities. A similar consortium of Universities of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has also been formed. Through the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa consortium of universities, various projects are run in connection with tapping higher education opportunities in China and formulation and executing various CPEC related projects.

A number of Pakistani Universities have entered into agreements and partnership with Chinese Universities. Many Universities in Pakistan have established China Study Center and many more are running Chinese's Language Learning Centers. In Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and particularly through Peshawar University, the establishment of China Study Centre and signing of Letter of Understanding between Pakistan Study Centre University of Peshawar and North West University Xian China merit mention.

Some universities in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa have taken initiatives in establishing institutions. The University of Peshawar has taken a lead by establishing the first ever China Study Centre (CSC) in the province. It was founded in 2016. The aim of the Centre is create linkages with China through research, learning, executing projects and people to people contacts. An introductory brochure of the Centre reads as:

“The Centre endeavors to pave the way for shaping a better future for the people of Pakistan generally and Khyber Pakhtunkhwa particularly. The CSC seeks to make the University of Peshawar a rich source of knowledge on China. To deepen local understanding of Chinese society, economy, culture, language, political system and vice versa. The CSC aims at achieving continuous progress through research and dissemination of information about China and Pakistan in a manner that is in tune with the expectations of the peoples of two friendly countries. To launch joint research projects through institutional collaboration and achieve the objectives of the Centre. The CSC will draw from the cultural, intellectual, and economic resources of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan to enrich and strengthen its programs and will strive for excellence in study, creative expression, and service to the country. The CSC strives to become an excellent Centre in research, learning and service in the region on China by producing research as per highest international standard. To equip research scholars with analytical thinking, innovative research methodologies, effective verbal and written communication that is critical for their pursuing careers in Pak-China Studies in an increasingly globalized marketplace. It will strive to develop academic collaboration with similar institutions and reinforce enriching interaction between China and Pakistan”

The other development in cooperation in higher education was the establishment of Pakistan Study Centre in China. The North West University Xian extended an invitation to University of Peshawar. In response to that, a 2-member delegation comprising of Prof. Dr. Fakhr-ul-Islam, Director Pakistan Study Center and Director China Study Centre Prof. Dr. Zahid Anwar Khan visited China from 9th to 15th May, 2018. The delegation attended International Conference under the auspices of Silk Road Educational Forum. During the conference, a “Letter of Understanding” was signed as a result of which Pakistan Study Centre was established in the North West University Xian. The delegation attended series of consultation regarding future plans of the newly established Centre.

Methodology

For this paper qualitative, quantitative and analytical methods have used. The study is quantitative because questionnaire method has been applied for measuring the advantages and challenges of CPEC. The data collected through questionnaire have been categorized into various tables with the help of SPSS software (22 version). It is analytical because the data have been analyzed with the help of frequency and percentage methods.

Qualitative Analysis

As for qualitative aspect of the research was concerned, schedule for key informant interviews was designed. It contained the following five questions:

- a. Do you think CPEC will be a success story?
- b. Do you think China is a sincere friend of Pakistan?
- c. What are the benefits of CPEC?
- d. Name the countries who are against this project.
- e. What are the challenges faced by CPEC?

In this regard, 8 people belonging to various parts of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa were approached. One half of them were those who were studying in various universities of China. A summary of their views is given below:

1. In International Relations there is no permanent friend or foe. National interest is the only thing nations seek. If a country foresees its interest in another country it will do anything to safeguard its interest. Since 73 years of Pakistan's inception there has been very little development in all the major sectors of the country, therefore, the government in 2013 realized that to make Pakistan a developed state we must focus our attention on industrialization; building of infrastructure and development of energy sector for which the internal resources of the country were inadequate. Due to lack of self-sufficiency, Pakistan had to look outward to external factors like foreign direct investment from China via CPEC. The track record of China giving loan is better as compared to the western states (USA, Germany, France or UK) as it has always completed the projects in a very short period of time instead of just giving plain loans. Corruption, incompetency and nepotism, the vices common in our culture, normally hinder in completion of mega-projects. However, the fact about CPEC is different. Under it, many developmental projects are getting completed.
2. CPEC is a classic manifestation of convergence of geostrategic and geo economic interest of the two partner countries with socio-economic and diplomatic relations fostered through vicissitudes of time. It is beneficial to both the countries. But China will be the greater beneficiary of this project as compared to Pakistan. To China it is a viable incentive to reach the oil-rich Middle East. A pipeline to transport crude oil from Gawadar to China's Xinjiang region will be extended. The pipeline is estimated to transmit a million barrels per day with its provisional capacity. China meets almost 50 per cent of its oil requirements from the Middle East, the pipeline will diversify its oil import routes. On the other hand, oil exporters of the Middle East will benefit from a cheaper and faster alternative to the existing route.
3. India is the first country who is openly working against CPEC and is creating hurdles for China and Pakistan. India openly spread terrorism by promoting insurgency in Balochistan. The province of Balochistan is the center point of CPEC Project, so, any turmoil in that province will have adverse impact on CPEC. India did not want to see a safe and financially sound Pakistan. The USA is also against the project. It has adopted double standards. As India is backed by the USA to contain China in the region, it will remain active both directly and indirectly. The United Arab Emirates' policy about Pakistan-China Economic Corridor is also not favorable. The UAE main concern about CPEC is that if Gawadar becomes duty-free port, then it will affect UAE's ports. They also have fears that if Gawadar becomes international deep sea port, then it will become the hub of international trade. To secure their own ports and trade they are tacitly opposing CPEC. Iran is also not at ease with the CPEC. The construction of an alternative seaport at Chabahar in coalition with India is a living example of that policy.
4. The major internal threats and challenges are political instability, terrorism and interference of countries who are against CPEC. Nevertheless, Pakistan and China are aware of these challenges. Pakistan has devised a strategy to keep all routes and projects of CPEC secure. A special division of Pakistan Army has been assigned the security duty. So it is hoped that both partner states will overcome these challenges.
5. The China-Pakistan Economic Corridor is for Pakistan and it will bring many benefits to all Pakistanis and with the hard work of both sides, the CPEC can achieve its goals. Some Pakistani laborers will get jobs. Other benefits include:
 - Many Pakistani products will be exported to China.

- CPEC is not only a road but the combinations of the road, rail and economic zones. All these projects will help Pakistani entrepreneurs.
 - Pakistan will no longer depend on the West.
 - Pakistani products will also be easily transported to other markets of the world.
6. CPEC might integrate the regional nations besides connecting them with Europe to Africa. This might result in creation of new markets on regional basis besides offering opportunities for new jobs.
 7. Due to the industrial and energy zones (which are parts of CPEC in Pakistan) the production of goods can increase in Pakistan and then Pakistan will also get a chance to export its goods to Central Asia and other parts of the world very easily. CPEC will bring immense economic opportunities for Pakistan. The country has for long faced economic crisis. In the wake of this project, Pakistan will seek revenue from port rents, trade tariffs and chance to establish its own trade links with the Gulf States
 8. Under the CPEC, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan would play an important role. It is expected that China is going to play a major role in the development of that province, keeping in view its strategic importance. Besides, China will build some industrial zone at sub-regional areas of KP, and will improve up on infrastructure of building, energy expansion, industrial growth and social expansion. It will be the test of KP government to properly consume the benefits of CPEC
 9. There has been very positive impact of CPEC on higher education. The Chinese government has been giving central attention to Pakistani students in scholarship quota. Pakistani students enjoyed maximum benefits in Chinese universities. Many young people from Khyber Pakhtunkhwa got the chance to pursue their higher studies thanks to CPEC. The success of CPEC is highly linked with the educational ties between Pakistan and China. The Chinese and Pakistani governments need to accelerate the educational progress and cooperation between the two countries.
 10. For Pakistan, CPEC may be a success story. It will be beneficial and successful in Pakistan if it helps to reduce poverty in the under-developed provinces of KP and Baluchistan. In this regard, the policy of the federal government needs to be corrected. Since Gawadar is the backbone of CPEC, therefore the poor people of Baluchistan in general and residents of Gawadar in particular be given maximum share in CPEC projects. After Balochistan, KP is the second under-developed province in Pakistan. These two provinces should be brought at par with the rest of the country. The Western route of CPEC is important and shortest one. It needs to be completed at the earliest. Abandoning of that route may cause a great loss to the people of KP. Further, CPEC will be a success story if the government of Pakistan is competent enough to take maximum advantages from it. Pakistan needs to convince China for more investment in agriculture and industrial sector. Pakistan's economy needs strong foundations which it lacks at the moment. Hopefully with CPEC, Pakistan will be able to overhaul its agriculture, industry; civil aviation, Railway, energy and other sectors.
 11. The Chinese government started giving more scholarships to the students of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. They also invited scholars and professors of different Pakistani universities to China to share views with them and to create more consensus on the CPEC. The ongoing cooperation between China and Pakistan in the field of higher education and languages studies is because of CPEC. Unfortunately, the students of Baluchistan are not getting that much share in the scholarships, which they need. Pakistani and Chinese should pay attention to it and accommodate students of Baluchistan. This will help to remove their suspicions and ill-feelings.
 12. The share of KP and Baluchistan provinces is very low. It should have been more than the other provinces, keeping in view their poverty and strategic locations in CPEC. The CPEC has two main areas of investments. First of all, the investments in energy projects and secondly investments in roads construction and developing Gwadar port. Besides Punjab and Sindh, energy generation projects may be formulated for KP and Balochistan. The Western-route which will benefit KP and Baluchistan should be restored and completed on time.

Quantitative analysis

A survey was conducted to ascertain opinion of people of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa regarding CPEC. The questionnaire for collecting quantitative data for this paper has half of the questions belonging to advantages while the remaining related to challenges of CPEC. The advantages of CPEC have been covered in terms of indicators like Pak-China friendship, the development of Pakistan's economy, infrastructural developments, and creation of job opportunities and access of Pakistan to the market of Europe, Middle East, Central Asia, Russia and Africa. The challenges of CPEC have been measured in the shape of indicators like opposition of USA and

others to CPEC, the effects of Chinese industry over local industry, law and order situation in Pakistan, cultural issues in Pakistan, and China's influence in Pakistan.

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) province of Pakistan was the universe of the study. A representative sampling has been taken from entire KP through convenient sampling technique. Keeping in view this technique, a total of 360 respondents have been taken as a sample. This study has two main variables i.e. advantages and challenges. Both these variables have been measured in terms of various indicators. All the indicators have been further measured on the basis of 5-point Likert Scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

The data have been analyzed with the help SPSS software (22 version). All the questions of the questionnaire were coded numerically and then fed in the software. Univariate analysis including frequency distribution and percentage methods were applied for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

The responses of respondents have been given in the following tables. After analyzing through SPSS, frequency percentage, valid percentage and cumulative percentage have been calculated.

Table 01: Strengthening Pak-China Friendship.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent	
Valid	Strongly Disagree	24	6.7	6.7	6.7
	Disagree	10	2.8	2.8	9.4
	Neutral	22	6.1	6.1	15.6
	Agree	110	30.6	30.6	46.1
	Strongly Agree	194	53.9	53.9	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0		

Table No. 01 shows that (53.9%) of the respondents are strongly agree that CPEC will further strengthen the Pak-China friendship. In informal discussion with the respondents, they opined that Pakistan is having a strong ties with China which can be further strengthened due to this project.

Table 02: Developing the Economy of Pakistan

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	18	5.0	5.0
	Disagree	16	4.4	9.4

Neutral	41	11.4	11.4	20.8
Agree	153	42.5	42.5	63.3
Strongly Agree	132	36.7	36.7	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0	

Majority of the respondents (42.5%) in Table No. 02 asserted that this project will develop the economy of Pakistan. They added that CPEC will develop many less developed areas of Pakistan particularly Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan.

Table 03: Infrastructural Development

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	13	3.6	3.6	3.6
Disagree	15	4.2	4.2	7.8
Neutral	30	8.3	8.3	16.1
Agree	143	39.7	39.7	55.8
Strongly Agree	159	44.2	44.2	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0	

A large number of the respondents (44.2%) in Table No. 03 demonstrated that this project will bring many infrastructural developments in Pakistan. They maintained that it will develop roads, motorway, railways, gas pipeline, power generation etc. which is need of the hour in Pakistan.

Table 04: Creation of Job opportunities in Pakistan

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	15	4.2	4.2
	Disagree	22	6.1	10.3
	Neutral	56	15.6	25.8
	Agree	147	40.8	66.7
	Strongly Agree	120	33.3	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 04 shows that unemployment is the main problem in Pakistan. An extensive number of the respondents (40.8%) asserted that this project will create many jobs in Pakistan. They added that it will improve their standard of living and lead to economic prosperity of the people especially in less developed areas of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa and Balochistan.

Table 05: Access of Pakistan to various World Markets

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	23	6.4	6.4
	Disagree	29	8.1	14.4
	Neutral	97	26.9	41.4
	Agree	141	39.2	80.6
	Strongly Agree	70	19.4	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0	

For economic development it is important that Pakistan get access to various world markets. Table No. 05 shows that majority of the respondents (39.2%) asserted that this project will enable Pakistan to get access to the markets of Europe, Middle East, Central Asia, Russia and Africa. It will in turn improve the economy of Pakistan.

Table 06: USA may create troubles for Pakistan

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Strongly Disagree	27	7.5	7.5	7.5
Disagree	44	12.2	12.2	19.7
Neutral	76	21.1	21.1	40.8
Agree	104	28.9	28.9	69.7
Strongly Agree	109	30.3	30.3	100.0
Total	360	100.0	100.0	

Table No. 06 gives opinion of the respondents about the role of USA. America wants to have a dominant status in South Asia. The emerging role of China is a major threat to the USA interest in this region. CPEC therefore can bring some problems for Pakistan created by USA and its allies. Responding to this perception, (30.3%) of the respondents are of the opinion that USA may create some problems for Pakistan due to CPEC.

Table 07: The Effects of Chinese Industry on Local Industry in Pakistan

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	Strongly Disagree	17	4.7	4.7	4.7
	Disagree	54	15.0	15.0	19.7
	Neutral	75	20.8	20.8	40.6
	Agree	114	31.7	31.7	72.2
	Strongly Agree	100	27.8	27.8	100.0
	Total	360	100.0	100.0	

In Table No. 07, the respondents have expressed opinion. According to them, the installation of Chinese industry under CPEC will bring industrial development in Pakistan. However, it may also affect the local Pakistani industry. About (31.7%) of the respondents maintained that the project of CPEC will affect the local industry.

Table 08: Challenges to CPEC in the Form of Law and Order Situation

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	21	5.8	5.8
	Disagree	67	18.6	24.4
	Neutral	116	32.2	56.7
	Agree	115	31.9	88.6
	Strongly Agree	41	11.4	100.0
	Total	360	100.0	100.0

Table No. 08 shows that the implementation of CPEC project will be a hard task due to bad law and order situation in Pakistan. About (31.9%) of the respondents asserted that there would be challenges in the implementation of the project.

Table 09: Cultural Challenges to Pakistan

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	27	7.5	7.5	7.5
	Disagree	76	21.1	21.1	28.6
	Neutral	78	21.7	21.7	50.3
	Agree	123	34.2	34.2	84.4
	Strongly Agree	56	15.6	15.6	100.0
	Total	360	100.0	100.0	

With the implementation of the CPEC project, there will be the influx of the Chinese in Pakistan. As a result, Chinese culture will be penetrated in Pakistani society. Pointing out the challenge of the Chinese culture, in Table No. 09, 34.2% of the respondents highlighted that this cultural diffusion will be challenge to Pakistani society.

Table 10: China's influence in Pakistan

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Disagree	48	13.3	13.3	13.3
	Disagree	73	20.3	20.3	33.6
	Neutral	63	17.5	17.5	51.1
	Agree	99	27.5	27.5	78.6
	Strongly Agree	77	21.4	21.4	100.0
	Total	360	100.0	100.0	

Widespread propaganda was launched by adversaries of CPEC that China will influence Pakistani society. However in Table No. 10. Only 27.5% of the respondents agree that Chinese's influence will affect Pakistani society.

Conclusion

The analysis of qualitative and quantitative data reveals that China Pakistan Economic Corridor has been taken quite positive in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The views of experts and relevant people who were interviewed clearly indicate tremendous support for CPEC and its interventions. To them China is the trusted friend of Pakistan. They hoped that CPEC can usher an era of prosperity in Pakistan. They did mention some international and regional adversaries to the project but hoped that Pakistan and China will be able to cope with them. Apart from international challengers, the respondents pointed out some other potential problems that may be faced by CPEC. There might be possible differences between Centre and provinces in Pakistan in terms of share of the federating units. The provinces-federation friction may be comparatively severe in the smaller provinces, particularly in Balochistan, than Punjab. The government of Pakistan needs to focus on Balochistan where anti-state elements are active on the sidelines of CPEC routes. Besides ensuring security of the route, government should win hearts of the general masses of the province by including more projects of socio-economic development.

As the study pertained to Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province, therefore the respondents mentioned it specifically. Besides showing satisfaction over the sincerity of China, they opined that the province is strategically important which may be a vigorous actor in successful implementation of CPEC. Although some of them expressed reservations about share in projects given to the province by the federal government, so they suggested that the grievances of the province need to be addressed. They were however, hopeful that the provincial government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa will be able to take up these issues with quarters concerned and will resolve them amicably. The respondents were unanimous on the point that satisfaction of provinces about their share in CPEC is internal problem of Pakistan and China had nothing to do with it. To them mutual trust and constant consultations between the two partners (China and Pakistan), is the only way to overcome difficulties.

The results of the survey were extremely encouraging. The overall result was that the people of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa are very much in favor of CPEC. In their view CPEC project is more beneficial for Pakistan, as 44.12% of them count its advantages. On the other hand only 31.12%. Of the respondents talked about its disadvantages and challenges. Thus, CPEC project is more advantageous for Pakistan. The overall opinions expressed by the respondents are given in the following graph:

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